

EFFECTIVE USE OF INTEGRATION IN CONDUCTING LANGUAGE CLASSES

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As we know, the language is a whole system, and it is impossible to understand it at a complete and sufficient level without knowing the internal laws existing in this system, without taking into account the dialectical unity of language rules with each other. In the learning process, integration is built on the basis of comparison, and it is flawed to make concepts that have no similarities into an object of comparison.

Without knowing the lexical-grammatical signs of any linguistic concept, it is impossible to understand the nature of the relationship between them, and thus, to understand the necessary, objective relationships in the chain of linguistic phenomena.

Taking this aspect into account, Professor Hasan Baliyev wrote: "The teacher should provide the students with the most necessary knowledge about grammatical concepts and concepts, and also take care of their acquisition of the skills specified in the program for individual sections".

After the mastered concept is examined in integration with another one according to its main and additional features, their use in speech practice is realized. Degree, time, quantity signs are not possible without a grammatical object. In the research work, we have paid attention to the integrative teaching of linguistics sections, and we have investigated the possibilities of intra- and interdisciplinary integration in mastering language rules.

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Language rules, which are generally called "grammatical knowledge", have been widely discussed in scientific and pedagogical literature. In one sense, it has been suggested that learning the rules facilitates acquisition.

One of a number of content directions or lines intended to be implemented in the teaching of the Azerbaijani language is the integration of knowledge and skills on "Language rules".

By learning the rules of the language, students get acquainted with the phonetic, lexical and grammatical structure of the language, and have concrete, clear and simple concepts about them. The teaching of rules and interpretations in an integrated form enables the formation and development of correct language and speech skills of students, and helps to understand the most necessary linguistic concepts and concepts. [6, 88-89]

Integration is also an enabler of succession. If we pay attention to the new textbooks and teaching aids, it can be seen that many elements of traditional education have preserved themselves in the content of the Azerbaijani language course, in the system of its acquisition.

Although the new textbooks devote a lot of space to the practical, practical nature, the role of the language rule as a mediator has not been ignored.

Apart from the primary class, the theoretical knowledge of language rules mainly starts in class V, where the possibilities of in-text integration are widely used. If we pay attention to additional resources to the textbook, the integration is mainly based on the content, structure and analysis of the text, not on the language order.

It is possible to observe such a relationship in most of the standards. If we compare the new textbook with the old textbook, we can observe how the succession is expected and the innovations.

If we consider the intra-disciplinary communication system, we will see that intra-disciplinary commu-

nication itself is based on intra-linguistic communication. This connection in language manifests itself as the unity and difference of language and thinking. Language as a system begins with phonetics (phonemes), and is completed in text syntax and speech. Experience also shows that words are learned in connection with sound.

Each process manifests itself in the activity before and after it. When a language fact does not connect to each other like a cogwheel, the system stops moving, speech, expression, law, method are incomplete. For example, mastering language rules is done in parallel with teaching sounds and letters. [2, 111]

In the process of teaching the first 3 sounds (a, n, t), the student gets acquainted with the rules of the language, and the following result is obtained:

- 1) recognizes these sounds and can pronounce them correctly;
- 2) is able to write and read words through those sounds;
- 3) can distinguish the sound and letter composition of the word;
- 4) can distinguish vowel and consonant sounds in the word with the help of signs;
- 5) understands dividing words into parts, that words consist of syllables;
- 6) Can form sentences by looking at pictures or using words;
- 7) understands that the number of syllables in a word corresponds to the number of vowels in it.

Entertaining games are provided in such an integrated way, speech sounds are presented simulating the sounds of animate and inanimate objects in nature. Learning achievements gained through the sounds and letters taught in grades V-XI can be systematized as follows:

1. Understands the difference between sound and letter.
2. Understands that words are formed from sounds.

3. Able to distinguish between vowel and consonant sounds.
4. Learns the syllabic structure of the word.
5. Understands the number of vowels in syllables and words.
6. He is able to ask questions about the word.
7. Gets acquainted with the types of grammatical meaning of the word, distinguishes the words denoting name, sign, number, action, recognizes the graphic sign.
8. Acquires the ability to construct a sentence.
9. Realizes that the suffixes -lar2 create the concept of quantity (plurality).
10. An initial idea about the root and suffix of the word is formed.
11. He is able to distinguish phrases and sentences, learns to express them orally and in writing.
12. Gets knowledge and experience about homonymy, synonymy and antonymy of words.
13. Gets acquainted with some pronunciation rules of words containing k, q consonants.
14. Acquires basic information about complex words. [2, 120-121]

During the teaching of the language rules to be learned, students learn those rules with new methods. Unlike traditional textbooks, tests on language rules are taught in new textbooks under logical headings such as "think and answer" and "true-false".

In the newly published textbooks, intra-disciplinary communication is mastered first in the integration of speech parts, then the constituent parts and structure of the word. Of course, it is impossible to talk about its composition and structure without words.

In fact, the foundation of phonetic education is laid during the literacy period, during which students are introduced to syllable sequences and events, even if they are primitive. Through subject mastery, they learn that the first habits related to literary pronunciation and writing are created by giving priority to studies and tasks based on the comparison of sound and letter composition. [3, 69]

The comparison of sound with words gives effective results, and in a kind of beginning, the foundation of the teaching of phonetics with orthography and

spelling is laid. By working on specific descriptions (e.g. filling in the blanks), students learn about the social nature of voice, its types, the role of voice in speech, etc. they gain initial familiarity with the issues.

Data on the teaching of language rules related to phonetics, orthography, and spelling are quite extensive in terms of both content standards and volume. Knowledge of those rules is strengthened through studies and tests.

By mobilizing integration opportunities, students' theoretical knowledge about sounds and letters is expanded and clarified. At the end of this lesson, students master the following about sounds and letters:

- 1) that words are formed from the combination of sounds;
- 2) sounds are divided into two groups, vowels and consonants;
- 3) that letters are signs of sounds in writing;
- 4) that the sound is heard, and the letter is visible by writing.

In the course of the lesson, students simultaneously strengthen their knowledge of the rules of spelling and pronunciation of words. [4, 25]

They clearly see that when pronouncing vowel sounds, the air flow does not encounter any obstacles in the oral cavity, while in consonants, on the contrary, the voice encounters various obstacles in the oral cavity.

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